

Available online at: <https://ijact.in>

Date of Submission	12/04/2020
Date of Acceptance	27/06/2020
Date of Publication	10/07/2020
Page numbers	3733-3742 (10 Pages)

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

ISSN:2320-0790

LEGAL REGULATION AND APPLICATION OF BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY IN THE CIVIL LAW OF THE RUSSIAN FEDERATION

Aleksei Yu. Churilov

PhD, Analyst at Tomsk State University, Scientific Educational Center “Intellectual Property and Intellectual Rights”, Russian Federation
Email: al.churilov@rambler.ru

Abstract: The article is dedicated to the assessment of blockchain technology from the point of view of the prospects of legal regulation and the possibility of using it in business and other activities, considering the legal field of the Russian Federation. The methodological basis of the study is a set of methods of scientific knowledge among which the main place is occupied by the methods of historicism, systematicity and analysis. The paper considers such technical features of blockchain systems that have a direct impact on both current and future legal regulation of relations emerging in connection with the use of blockchain systems.

Results: The blockchain technology is examined from the point of view of performing the functions of the payment system and other methods of application such as using distributed information storage, decentralized decision-making as a replacement for traditional contracts. The article presents a study of the views on the legal nature of a smart contract considering changes in civil law. The author examines in detail the nature of a smart contract as an agreement at the three stages of its dynamics: conclusion, execution and violation. The article discusses the features of blockchain technology that predetermine the features of smart contracts and the specifics of their application.

Conclusions: The definition of the place of a smart contract in the system of civil law agreements is proposed. A smart contract, taking into account its features is a contractual design and not a contract form, which has the following characteristics: conclusion and existence in exclusively electronic form in the blockchain system; automatic execution of an emerging counter contractual obligation without the need for a separate expression of the will of the parties to the contract; the impossibility of changing the smart contract after it was posted on the blockchain network even by agreement of the parties. The classification of named civil contracts in terms of the possibility of their existence in the form of a smart contract design was carried out.

Keywords: cryptocurrency, blockchain, agreement, smart contract, obligation, money, joint-stock company

I. INTRODUCTION

A. What Is a Blockchain?

The first mention of Blockchain technology can be found in a work written by a person or group of people under the pseudonym Satoshi Nakamoto, “Bitcoin: A Peer-to-Peer Electronic Money System” [1]. Before considering the features of the application and legal regulation of this technology, it is necessary to highlight the basics and features of its functioning.

Blockchain is a database distributed among all devices included in the Blockchain Network, using which users transmit information. As you know, any information including information about transactions can be represented by the amount of data it contains. And the information about transactions in the blockchain system represents the amount of data combined in a kind of links, which in turn are chronologically combined into a chain of blocks in which each previous block confirms the validity of the next by including information about previous transactions in the form of a special cryptographic key in the header of each

subsequent transaction block. Thus, each block is identified using a cryptographic key, a hash, which is generated using the SHA256 cryptographic algorithm [2]. Herewith, each of the network participants stores at least part of the entire database, which ensures its resistance to illegal actions by both third parties and the participants themselves. The blockchain technology can be identified as the transformed concept of clusters [3].

B. Blockchain Technology and Anonymity

A key feature of the technology under consideration is the absence of any center for monitoring and managing transactions carried out on the blockchain network since transactions are confirmed using a special cryptographic mechanism. The main way to confirm transactions remain ensuring of their publicity: each transaction in the system is transmitted by all devices on the network and the entry recorded in the public transaction ledger (shared public ledger) only after confirmation on their part. So this technology developer cannot theoretically affect the integrity and reliability of transactions.

Transaction anonymity is mistakenly considered a feature of blockchain technology [4]. Indeed, to use the Bitcoin cryptocurrency as a general rule, there is no need to register or otherwise identify yourself. You just need to specify the email address and the desired password. To use the system, a pair of public keys is used, a private key, with the help of which transactions are carried out in the system without disclosing the identity of the sender and recipient. However, according to the fair assertion of foreign researchers, such a system should be called pseudo-anonymous rather than anonymous [5]. Due to the pseudo-anonymous nature of the blockchain, it is impossible to fully agree with the statement that this technology allows “to reliably record reliable data on the ownership of an existing digital asset to a specific person (highlighted by the author)” [6]. The fact is that a pair of public and private key pair is not determined by a specific person, but rather by a specific IP address or email, and it is not necessary to own a private key that provides access to the virtual units of the blockchain network. Consequently, the reliability of an asset’s ownership can only be talked about in relation to a public key, but not to any specific person, since, as a general rule, it is unknown.

C. Blockchain Technology Generations

In connection with the popularization of blockchain technology in the world two generations of the development of this technology are distinguished: Blockchain 1.0, which symbolizes cryptocurrency only and Blockchain 2.0, which includes other methods of application, such as smart contracts, “smart property”, distributed storage of information [7]. Thus, at present, blockchain technology is used in two main ways:

- 1) as a payment system for creating and conducting transactions with cryptocurrency;
- 2) other types of use, including smart contracts.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Methodology

It is represented by methods of analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction as well as a comparative method. Extensive normative and theoretical material on the problems of using blockchain technology in its various fields was studied: payment system, smart contracts, collegial decision-making, and distributed storage of information.

B. Advantages and Disadvantages of Cryptocurrency

Currently, more and more attention is paid to cryptocurrency in the literature. Despite attempts to legislatively determine the place of cryptocurrency in the system of civil rights, the category of “digital money” has not been introduced into the Civil Code of the Russian Federation and therefore the question of the legal nature of cryptocurrency is still open. For formation of competitive, highly-effective, and sustainable information economy in modern Russia, it is necessary to pay attention to the issues of development of E-government and spheres of new information and communication technologies [8].

The main disadvantage of using cryptocurrency as a means of payment is its uncertain legal status. Thus, the US tax service recognizes cryptocurrency, in particular, Bitcoin, as property [9]. There is no single position on the legal nature of cryptocurrency among the courts of the United States. Some judges consider it to be money [10], some do not recognize cryptocurrency as money [11]. Commodity Futures Trading Commission considers cryptocurrency as a digital commodity [12]. Cryptocurrency is considered as “private money” in Germany, and from January 1, 2020, banks, subject to certain conditions, can carry out cryptocurrency storage operations [13]. In particular, it is forbidden to determine prices in Bitcoins, sell and buy Bitcoins, exchange Bitcoins for national or foreign currencies, render any other services related to Bitcoins to customers, etc. [14] At one time, the European Court ruled that operations with Bitcoin are exempt from value-added tax (VAT) in accordance with the legislative provisions on currencies, banknotes and coins used as legal tender [15]. Simplicity is the magic that has turned Bitcoin from a game into powerful tool [16].

Cryptocurrency is a type of virtual currency. The first definition of virtual currency was given by the European Central Bank in 2012. In accordance with it, virtual currency is a type of unresolved digital money issued and controlled by the creators and used, and accepted among members of a particular virtual community [17].

Cryptocurrency cannot be attributed to money in their classical sense. From the point of view of the commodity theory of money, proceeding from the fact that money is an ordinary commodity but accepted everywhere, which is a kind of “good averaging”, it is impossible to recognize cryptocurrency as money because few are willing to accept it as payment and its value is extremely volatile and determined depending on the mood of the market in

connection with which it is impossible to consider it as an “averaging” product. From the point of view of the state-legal theory of money, proceeding from the fact that money is only what a special state act gave to the power of money, cryptocurrency cannot be recognized as money since in no state it is recognized as a legal means of payment. L. A. Lunts rightly emphasized that the state cannot give legal entities legal tender if an economic participant rejects such an asset, not wanting to use it as an “instrument of exchange” for transactions [18]. From the legal and economic point of view, money is an established means of payment to which the power of money has been given by a state act. With regard to cryptocurrency, the Central Bank of the Russian Federation noted at the time that according to Article 27 of the Federal Law “On the Central Bank of the Russian Federation (Bank of Russia)”, the issue of monetary surrogates in the Russian Federation is prohibited [19]. However, there is no legal definition of quasi-cash in the Russian Federation. Moreover, the doctrine also discusses the definition of a monetary substitute, its characteristics, and its place in civil circulation [20]. In this regard, it should be agreed that in order to recognize cryptocurrency as a monetary surrogate, it is necessary to have at least a normative definition of the quasi-cash. It should be admitted that cryptocurrency cannot be recognized, contrary to the opinion of a number of researchers [21], as quasi-cash.

C. Cryptocurrency in the Exchange Process

Considering cryptocurrency from the point of view of performing the mentioned functions of money, it should be noted that it cannot perform these functions to one degree or another. Cryptocurrency is not a measure of value, since it itself, like a commodity, has an ever-changing value. Based on the value of the cryptocurrency, it is exchanged for goods whose value is determined, as a rule, in the currency as a legal means of payment, or taking into account the value of the cryptocurrency in relation to this currency. Cryptocurrency cannot fulfill the function of money as a means of circulation in civil circulation due to its un-recognition by the state as legal tender. Cryptocurrency cannot act as money as a means of circulation, that is, an object that all market participants are ready and obligated to accept as payment for the goods they produce for the simple reason that only a narrow circle of participants in civil turnover is ready to accept it as a means of payment. Cryptocurrency cannot also fulfill the function of world money to serving international economic relations, and to be recognized as a global and universal means of payment because it is not a reserve currency or the currency of foreign economic transactions and practically has not its part in exchange or payment in the international circle of goods and services. The exception became the rare exceptions, made possible by the development of cross-border Internet commerce.

D. Cryptocurrency and Money

Not being cash, cryptocurrency is also not a thing, since corporeal and physically tangible objects are recognized as things. Cryptocurrency cannot be recognized as an object

of ownership in the strict sense of this concept. In fact, “ownership” of cryptocurrency means only that on the “wallet” of the owner of the public and private keys there are records about the execution of a certain number of cryptocurrency transactions in relation to this “wallet,” the amount of which is the balance of the “wallet,” the public key. Cryptocurrency is not non-cash money since it is in the direct “possession” of the owner and is not in the bank account, representing only an entry in the public account book of transactions made with cryptocurrency.

It is impossible to consider cryptocurrency as a mandatory proprietary right (right to claim), because, firstly, the content of such a requirement is difficult to determine; secondly, there is no entity to which such a requirement is addressed; thirdly, relations on the circulation and creation of cryptocurrency are not binding, since the blockchain technology allows you to transfer cryptocurrency from one use to another directly, bypassing any government agency as an intermediary or controller.

E. Civil Laws and Cryptocurrency

At first glance, cryptocurrency resembles electronic money, but it is not one. The turnover of electronic funds always presupposes the existence of an intermediary in the use of traditional funds, a legal tender. Moving cryptocurrency from user to user does not imply the existence of an intermediary in the sense that is given to this phenomenon by the legislator. Of course, as an intermediary, you can consider the blockchain system itself within which the transaction is performed but such a representation of the procedure for moving the cryptocurrency does not fit into the framework of domestic legislation. Moreover, cryptocurrency cannot be considered a payment system in the sense that is defined in paragraph 20 of art. 3 Federal Law “On the National Payment System”: firstly, there are no higher organizations and operators in the cryptocurrency payment system since users interact only among themselves in a peer-to-peer network, and secondly, this system is not regulated by the rules of the payment system, established by Russian or other legislation.

Cryptocurrency is also not a foreign currency within the meaning of Federal Law of 10.12.2003 No. 173-FZ “On Currency Regulation and Currency Control” [22] since it is not a legal tender in any foreign country.

F. Cryptocurrency in the Framework of Civil Rights

Attempts of squeezing cryptocurrency into the framework of the existing list of civil rights objects (particularly, in other property), not seem to be correspond of the cryptocurrency nature. A cryptocurrency is an object of a special kind of rights that does not have material embodiment. It is impossible to agree that we are talking about a material object created by means of material devices using the material (electromagnetic) properties of matter, the creation and possession of which requires the expenditure of electrical energy [23]. Attempts to extend the mode of things to cryptocurrency are doomed to failure due to the peculiarity of the technical nature of this phenomenon. At present, cryptocurrency cannot be reliably

assigned to any type of civil rights object. This makes it appropriate to amend the Civil Code in order with including such civil law object as “cryptocurrency” or “virtual currency” (according to some authors) in the provisions on civil rights objects [24]. So the absence of legislative regulation remains only one possible place for cryptocurrency in the system of civil rights like a different property.

Failure to recognize cryptocurrency as money as well as legal means of payment entails serious restrictions on their use in civil circulation.

Unlike legal means of payment, which are cash and non-cash money, electronic money and cryptocurrency cannot be recognized as legal tender, because they do not have the property of unconditionally accepting them as money, and the lender's consent is required to fulfill a monetary obligation with electronic money. So, for example, it is unacceptable to fulfill an overdue monetary obligation for a debtor by a third party according to the rules of clause 2 of Article 313 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation, if a third party wants to make such a performance with cryptocurrency or electronic money. In this case, the creditor does not have an unconditional obligation to accept such a performance.

III. OTHER WAYS TO USE BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY

A. *Smart Contracts*

The most controversial use of blockchain technology is the so-called “smart” contracts, which are contracts that are automatically executed by a computer [25]. Russian scientists in the most general form define a smart contract as a programmed contract, the terms of which are written in the program code and which is automatically executed using the blockchain [26]. There are more comprehensive definitions of a smart contract. For example: “A smart contract is a contract that exists in the form of program code implemented on the Blockchain platform, which ensures the autonomy and self-fulfilment of the terms of such contract in the circumstances predetermined therein occurrence” [6]. Automation of this kind ensures its execution through the use of certain program code with almost complete exclusion from the human process. Moreover, smart contracts, in the first place are executed not under the influence of the possibility of state coercion, but through technical coercion. It should be noted that some researchers consider smart contracts not as a contract, but as a full replacement for both the contract and the classical legal regulation as a whole, implying that “the code is the law” [27]. However, even Thomas Hobbes wrote that “if there is a common power standing above both sides that has the right and the strength to force them to implement the agreement, then it really is” [28]. The basic idea is that even self-executing contracts, the conclusion and execution of which do not require intervention by the competent authorities, require appropriate legislative regulation. The need for an add-on, including the legal one, was also argued by K. Marx [29]. Consequently, the existence of smart contracts seems

unthinkable without the legal basis for such an existence, and, according to foreign researchers, they will not replace classical contracts, and as a result, they do not undermine the need for the existence of contract law [30].

The idea of a smart contract was first described back in 1997 by lawyer and economist Nick Szabo [31]. He defined a smart contract as a computer protocol that independently executes transactions, as well as controlling their execution, during the implementation of which a violation of the contract becomes economically unjustified. One of the prototypes of smart contracts, the author called machines selling various goods. Indeed, if the machine works properly, when you deposit money into your account and select the goods, the contract of sale is executed automatically. A smart contract really “blindly” performs the functions laid down in it, which does not allow us to fully recognize it as “smart” [32].

On March 18, Federal Law No. 34-FZ of March 18, 2019, “On Amending Parts One, Two, and Article 1124 of Part Three of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation,” was adopted [33], which from October 1, 2019, introduced into the Civil Code provisions on smart contracts and digital rights. In this regard, there is again a need to assess the legal nature of smart contracts in the light of changes in civil law.

There are many services you can use the technology of “smart” contracts: Ethereum, BlockStream, etc. It is necessary to determine whether a “smart” contract can be considered as a contract, i.e. an agreement of two or more persons on the establishment of a change or termination of civil rights and obligations. Firstly, as a result of concluding a smart contract, rights and obligations do arise in accordance with the conditions under which this contract is concluded. Secondly, when performing actions aimed at concluding a smart contract and, accordingly, an agreement, the parties express their will to reach an agreement, which indicates the strong-willed nature of these actions. One of the problems associated with the recognition of a smart contract as a contract, in relation to domestic law, is the form of such a contract. In accordance with the Civil Code, a contract in writing can be concluded by drafting one document (including electronic) signed by the parties or by exchanging letters, telegrams, electronic documents or other data that can reliably identify the person from whom the expression of origin.

The identification of the parties, as already noted, is the most serious problem. In this regard, the question arises: is it possible to consider the use of a private key for concluding a contract as an electronic signature? In accordance with the legislation of the Russian Federation, an electronic signature is information in electronic form that is attached to other information in electronic form (signed information) or is otherwise associated with such information, and which is used to determine the person signing the information [34]. As a general rule, participants in blockchain systems do not disclose their identity, but it is possible to include information about the contracting parties in the code of the smart contract. Therefore, subject to the conditions for identification of the parties, the use of a private key can be considered as an electronic signature. Regarding the legal nature of the smart contract, there is no consensus to date. There are several main positions:

- a) an assignment of smart contracts to contracts [6].
- b) a smart contract is not a contract, but a way to execute it [35].
- c) a smart contract is just a form of contract [36].
- d) a smart contract is a form of self-defense of law [30].
- e) some researchers find it difficult to determine the legal nature of the smart contract [37].

Currently, among native and foreign researchers, the position consideration smart contracts as contracts prevail [6]. Firstly, as a result of the conclusion of such a “smart” contract, rights and obligations do arise in accordance with the conditions on which this contract is concluded. Secondly, when committing actions aimed at concluding a smart contract, the parties express their will to reach an agreement, which indicates the strong-willed nature of these actions. Researchers classify smart contracts as “strong”, which it is not economically feasible to challenge or change in court, and “weak”, which is possible and appropriate to change in court [38].

It is impossible to study any legal phenomenon without taking care of the prevailing doctrine and legal norms. It is necessary to determine the smart contract place in the contract law system to detail its review. Some authors deny the possibility of recognizing a smart contract as an independent fact. And this opinion has to seem correct [26]. At the same time, it can be a simplification of the essence and features of a smart contract, reducing it only to an electronic contract form as some researchers have suggested [39]. If we are taking care of the features of smart contracts it seems most reasonable to attribute such contracts more to a contractual design than to reduce their legal nature only to an agreement form.

To determine the place of a smart contract in the contract system, it is necessary to study the dynamics of the contractual relationship at three main stages:

1. The conclusion of a smart contract.
2. Fulfillment of a contractual obligation from a smart contract.
3. Consequences of breach of contractual obligation from a smart contract.

B. The Conclusion of a Smart Contract

An agreement shall be deemed concluded if an agreement has been reached between the parties in the form required in the required cases on all the essential terms of the agreement. One should agree with the opinion about such a sign of “smart” contracts as their focus on the disposal of primarily digital assets [6] due to the almost complete unsuitability for the disposal of tangible, rather than digital, assets. In this regard, some researchers define a smart contract in a narrower sense as automated programs that ensure the transfer of digital goods to the blockchain network when any condition occurs [40].

In relation to smart contracts, it is necessary to consider the features of the offer and acceptance, the form of the smart contract, as well as the counter-provision that is characteristic of the countries of the Anglo-Saxon legal system.

The offer and acceptance do not seem to differ from the offer and acceptance in classical contracts. Only one feature distinguishes a smart contract from the classical methods of concluding a contract: acceptance, as a general

rule, is accomplished by performing an act of acceptance by an acceptor. The fact of placing the contract on the network is an offer containing all the essential terms of the contract. In this case, acceptance, for example, on the Ethereum network, is made by transferring a certain virtual unit to the provider's account [41]. In this regard, the question arises: from the point of view of the moment of conclusion of the contract, is it possible to attribute a smart contract to a real deal? As the researchers note, the Latin word *res* (thing) gave rise to the concept of a real contract, according to which the emergence of rights and obligations is associated with the active actions of at least one of the parties to the transaction, namely, actions to transfer to the other side the property due to it [42]. At the same time, one should not equate the transfer of property to conclude a real contract and the transfer of property due to the party, since the property is not always due to the party, but only relates to the subject of the obligation, for example, under a real contract for the carriage of goods, the property transferred is not due to the carrier, this object relates with the subject of the obligation, actions of the parties for the carriage of goods. Since we are talking about property, it is necessary to determine whether such a token is a property in the sense attached to this phenomenon by law. Obviously, there is no reason to recognize cryptocurrency and tokens necessary for concluding a smart contract as a material object (thing), as some researchers do, justifying their position by the fact that we are talking about created using material devices using material (electromagnetic) properties matter, the creation and possession of which requires the expenditure of electrical energy [23]. Such a logical chain will make it possible to recognize as a thing, including ECM programs. At present, assigning tokens and cryptocurrencies to “other property” seems to be the most justified from the point of view of legislation in the absence of other acceptable alternatives. This point of view was also confirmed by the Law, attributing digital rights to other property. Therefore, the transfer of property in the form of a token, necessary for concluding a contract, allows you to classify a smart contract as a group of real contracts, but only if the transferred token is related to the subject of the obligation.

Recall that the terms of such an agreement are fixed using programming languages and are formulated according to the model of an accession agreement, which also reduces the scope of application of smart contracts, excluding from it, at present, agreements for the conclusion of which pre-negotiation negotiations are important. At the same time, the approval of the terms of a smart contract at the stage of negotiating a contract is potentially acceptable.

The issue of counter-provision, which is necessary for the enforceability of the contract in the English-Saxon legal system, is also solved by researchers in favor of smart contracts, since, as a general rule, there are no free smart contracts, and counter-provision of parties is fixed in its code by default [38]. There is a completely opposite point of view, according to which smart contracts do not contain a counter provision [30].

There is a problem which smart contracts cannot solve. It is the problem of determining the proper party to the contract, in case if such one contract was concluded by an incompetent or partially incapable person. It is sure that this problem is generally inherent to e-commerce. For

example, it is impossible to reliably determine who exactly uses a credit card in the time of purchase making.

In this regard, some researchers suggest considering smart contracts and their algorithms, even computers as representatives of individuals or their agents who make transactions, since, from a formal point of view, the agreement is concluded not by persons, but keys [30, 43]. With regard to the Russian legal system, such a proposal cannot be recognized as being implemented and complying with the legislation, since a representative can be a fully capable person, while the legal capacity of computers and algorithms, at present, is domestic, and any other legislation is not recognized.

Based on the peculiarities of constructing the program code for a “smart” contract according to the if-then type, it can be said that such an agreement always forms a counter obligation.

It is difficult to agree that a characteristic feature is an increased degree of certainty of the contract [6]. It is impossible to include all the necessary, and in relation to some contracts, and essential, conditions in the program code, which is the terms of the contract, which in practice can just lead to lengthy litigation, and not save the parties from them. Smart contracts also do not pass the problem of reality when providing false assurances, as well as in the case of a significant misconception of the parties, since it can clearly be argued that the program code containing the terms of the smart contract is compiled by people who may be mistaken in the transaction, or enter the counterparty misleading.

From the point of view of domestic legislation, an interesting issue is the form of a smart contract as a contract. In accordance with the Law, amendments will be made to Article 160 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation, according to which, the written form of the transaction is considered to be observed also if the person completes the transaction using electronic or other technical means, allowing the contents of the transaction to be reproduced on a physical medium, while the requirement for a signature is considered fulfilled if any method is used to reliably determine the person who expressed the will. Therefore, we can confidently conclude that the legislator will equate the smart contract with the written form of the transaction.

A smart contract, considering the technological features of blockchain systems, can exist exclusively in electronic form, which currently narrows its application scope. An example is a real estate lease agreement concluded for a time less than a year and subject to state registration. Currently, the legislation does not provide the agreement’s registering procedure without drawn up on paper and signed by the parties. Additionally, the legislator justifiably limited the scope of smart contracts application exclusively to contractual obligations, fixing in the Law (Article 3) that it is not allowed using electronic or other technical means.

According to a Civil Code, an agreement can be concluded by exchanging letters, telegrams, telexes, telefaxes and other documents, including electronic documents transmitted via communication channels. It makes possible to establish a reliable fact, a document came from a party

under an agreement. The identification of the parties, as has been noted more than once, is the most serious problem. In this regard, the question arises: is it possible to use a private key for concluding a contract as an electronic signature? The legislation of the Russian Federation tells us, an electronic signature is electronic information that is attached to other electronic information (signed information) or is otherwise associated with such information. It can be used to determine the person signing the information [34]. As a general rule, participants in the blockchain systems do not disclose their identity, but it’s possible to include information about the contracting parties in the code of the smart contract.

So if the conditions of parties’ identification were carried in, using a private key could be considered as an electronic signature.

C. Fulfillment of an Obligation from a Smart Contract

As a general rule, a contractual obligation is performed by the parties themselves voluntarily. In case of refusal to perform, the counterparty can be compelled in court to enforce the obligation in kind. A smart contract is executed independently without human intervention, and, as a rule, when it is impossible to influence it from the outside.

Since the obligation to conclude a smart contract is executed automatically, at first glance, no problems arise. The ability to enforce using computer code is a hallmark of smart contracts. It should be noted that the ability to ensure the proper fulfillment of an obligation through computer code, for example, by software methods, you can limit the possibility of transferring the acquired copyright [44] or limit the possibility of its use in strict accordance with the terms of the license agreement.

The legislator amended Art. 309 of the Civil Code, in particular by supplementing the provisions of Article 309 of the second part, in accordance with which the terms of the transaction may provide for the fulfillment by its parties of obligations arising from it upon the occurrence of certain circumstances without the additional expressions of the will expressed by the parties aimed at fulfilling the obligation by applying information technologies determined by the terms of the transaction. We are talking about such a thing as automated fulfillment of an obligation. In fact, the legislator solved the problem which could arise in resolving disputes related to the fulfillment of an obligation arising from a smart contract, the problem of will and will expression. Automated execution eliminates the need for a separate expression of will aimed at fulfilling the obligation, which raises the question of the validity of such legal action because from the point of view of the legal nature, execution is a transaction, and will and expression of will are one of the elements of the transaction. With amendments, this dispute was resolved in favor of the recognition of such performance as valid.

A feature of a smart contract is that, once it has been concluded and entered the blockchain, its conditions cannot be changed, which creates problems with a significant change in circumstances or the need to change its individual conditions, for example, the delivery address of the goods or in case of a change of parties to commitment. Insufficient elaboration of the smart contract code can lead

to improper execution of the contract. A small error in the code of the smart contract can send, for example, the ship to the wrong loading port, which the parties agreed at the negotiation stage.

Some foreign researchers consider the automatic execution of a smart contract like a form of law's self-defense [38]. It should be noted the theory of self-defense of the right to voluntarily fulfill an obligation is being developed in the native doctrine [45]. From this point of view, indeed, if the content of the smart contract is legal, its execution without the participation of the court using computer protocols can be considered as a kind of law self-defense, and will also correspond to the main signs of self-defense [46, 47]. It is a lawful act of a person (in relation to smart contracts, we can talk about lawful inaction, non-interference in the program in any way), aimed at removing the obstacle to the satisfaction of legitimate interests, carried out without resorting to the competent authorities, different from necessary defense and emergency.

Other researchers consider the possible to consider a smart contract as a mechanism similar to the escrow stipulated in the contract [30]. Indeed, when placing, depositing, a certain amount in the blockchain system, which will be transferred to the counterparty in the performance of the obligation. It can be argued the smart contract contains an escrow mechanism, with the only proviso that the blockchain system itself will act as an exclusion agent. However, such a design is currently not applicable within the Russian legal system. According to an Art. 926.7 of the Russian Federation's Civil Code in a conditional escrow agreement, the depositor agrees to transfer property to the escrow agent for the purpose of fulfilling the depositor's obligation to transfer it to another person in whose favor the property is deposited (to the beneficiary), and the escrow agent agrees to ensure the safety of this property and transfer it to the beneficiary if the grounds specified in the contract arise. In addition to the mandatory presence of a third-party figure, an escrow agent, in accordance with paragraph 3 of Art. 926.7, the escrow agreement is subject to notarization, which is not possible in the case of a smart contract.

Smart contracts are ideal if the parties to the contract have provisions on the conditional fulfillment of the obligation, since, as a general rule, the performance of duties, as well as the exercise, modification, and termination of certain rights under a contractual obligation from a smart contract is due to the fulfillment or non-fulfillment of one of the parties' obligations by certain actions or the onset of other circumstances, such as sending goods or receiving them, sending a token or cash, which is fully consistent with norm 327.1 of the Civil Code.

D. Breach of Contractual Obligation from a Smart Contract

The argument about the impossibility of violating an obligation from a smart contract seems invalid [48] and the lack of need for intermediaries in the form of courts, bailiffs and other law enforcement agencies [6]. There are many circumstances in which such an agreement may be violated: violation of the deadlines for the fulfillment of an obligation, delivery of low-quality goods, etc. First of all, this applies to contracts for the management of tangible,

not digital assets, but this alone casts doubt on the conclusion of the inviolability Smart contract. Moreover, an attacker can take over the private key of a person and enter into several contracts on his behalf, which in the future will need to be challenged in court.

Summing up, we can conclude that a smart contract, being an independent contractual design, has the following features:

- a) the conclusion and its existence in exclusively electronic form in the blockchain system;
- b) automatic execution of an arising counter contractual obligation without the need for a separate expression of the will of the parties to the contract;
- c) the impossibility of changing it after it was posted on the blockchain network, even by agreement of the parties.

It is appropriate to classify named civil contracts in terms of the possibility of their existence as a smart contract into two main groups:

1. Contracts, which can exist both in the form of smart contracts and in the traditional form. Most of the named contracts belong to such contracts.
2. Contracts that cannot be concluded in the form of smart contracts. These include a real estate lease agreement concluded for a period of at least one year and subject to state registration. Currently, the legislation of the Russian Federation does not provide for a procedure for registering an agreement other than drawn up on paper and signed by the parties.

E. Collegial Decision Making

A theoretically interesting and possible application of blockchain technology seems to be decentralized decision making. Currently, the admissibility of decision making using electronic and other technical means is enshrined in Art. 181.2 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation.

There are no legal obstacles to organizing remote participation in voting at the general meeting of shareholders, including using blockchain technology [49, 50]. However, the difficulties of applying such a procedure in the domestic law and order can be considered by the example of a general meeting of a joint-stock company. Of course, voting using blockchain technology must be considered as absentee, which, in accordance with Art. 60 Federal Law "On Joint Stock Companies", may be carried out, among other things, by filling out an electronic form of bulletins on the Internet [51]. Theoretically, it is possible to formulate a shareholder voting program code in such a way that it complies with the requirements for voting ballots. However, in the future, certain difficulties arise, not only of a legal but also of a technical nature. Firstly, the identification of the voting shareholder seems difficult, because, based on the very essence of the blockchain technology, it is not a person who votes, but a public key, the establishment of which constitutes a separate, but still solvable, problem. Secondly, when voting for shareholders, it is necessary to use systems different from the public blockchain, which imply the admission of each voter and the provision of a public-private key pair, which is difficult in societies with more than 500 thousand participants, for

which much more convenient mechanisms for holding absentee voting are provided. Thirdly, in relation to public joint-stock companies, due to the constant movement of shares, it is difficult to track new shareholders and the disappearance of old ones using blockchain technology. It should be concluded that with respect to large companies, at present, the use of blockchain technology for voting does not look promising.

F. Storage of Information, Including Personal Data

Currently, there are services that provide decentralized information storage services using blockchain technology for this which allows reducing costs while maintaining data security. So, the cost of storing one gigabyte of data on the Stroj service costs only \$ 0.015 per month. However, such distributed storage of information entails a number of risks. For example, in case of the detection of illegal content in the system, all users of this system can be blocked.

One of the rather interesting problems is the problem of compliance of blockchain technology with the requirements of the legislation on personal data: both domestic, expressed primarily in the Federal Law "On Personal Data", and European, expressed in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). It should be emphasized that the Regulation applies to the processing of personal data of data subjects located in the EU, not only by a person established in the EU, but by a controller or data processor by a person not established in the Union, if data processing concerns: the provision of goods and services to data subjects in The EU, regardless of whether payment is required from the specified data subject, or monitoring their activity, provided that the activity is carried out in the EU. Non-resident companies are subject to this Regulation, including if they use the official language of the EU Member State both in the description of goods/services and when placing orders; use the currency of the EU member state in settlements with customers; directly indicated on the website that goods/services are offered to EU citizens [52].

Personal data refers to any information relating directly or indirectly to a specific or determinable natural person (the subject of personal data) [53, 54]. At the same time, the GDPR, in contrast to domestic legislation, indicates who is an identifiable (defined) individual, a person who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular, through identifiers such as name, identification number, location information, identifier online or through one or more of the characteristics characteristic of the physical, psychological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of the specified individual. It can be concluded that both domestic and European legislators have adopted a "broad" approach to the definition of personal data. This approach allows you to attribute almost any information to personal data, including that which may be in the blockchain system, since even an IP address, including a dynamic one, refers to personal data according to the ECJ practice [55, 56].

There is no doubt that the data contained in the blockchain systems can be classified as personal data and their processing must comply with the requirements of legislation on the processing of personal data. Some authors, taking into account the special technological basis of blockchain technology, propose to exclude blockchain

systems containing personal data from the scope of legislation on the protection of personal data regarding the implementation of certain rights of personal data subjects [57].

It is necessary to consider the rights that are granted to personal data subjects in terms of the possibility of their implementation when using blockchain systems. The most important rights, the implementation of which may be difficult in the blockchain system, are the right to specify personal data; the right to oblivion; GDPR right to data portability from one platform to another.

- a) In accordance with **the right to clarify** personal data, the personal data subject has the right to demand the correction of inaccurate, incomplete and inaccurate personal data processed by the operator (Article 14 of the Federal Law "On Personal Data", Article 16 of the GDPR).
- b) **The right to be forgotten** is provided for by both the GDPR (Art. 17) and Art. 10.3 of the Federal Law "On Information, Information Technologies and the Protection of Information" and Art. 14 Federal Law "On Personal Data". It should be immediately emphasized the difference between the right to oblivion provided for by the GDPR and provided by domestic law. If the GDPR requires the deletion of personal data, then the domestic legislator grants the right to demand the suspension of links to pages on the Internet containing relevant information.
- c) In accordance with **the right to data portability**, the personal data subject has the right to receive the personal data relating to him that he provided to the controller in a structured, universal and machine-readable format; he has the right to transfer the specified data to another controller without hindrance from the controller, who was provided with personal data if their processing was based on consent and is carried out using automated means (Article 20 of the GDPR).

The complexity of the implementation of these rights is associated with the technological feature of the blockchain systems, namely, the invariability of the information in it. Due to the fact that data in the blockchain system can only be added, but not changed or deleted from it, the realization of the right of the subject of personal data to clarify or destroy personal data is impossible. It is equally impossible to transfer such data to another controller since the technical features of blockchain systems make such movement impossible.

IV. CONCLUSION

Thus, the blockchain technology is certainly promising and will only continue to develop, however, technological features lead to problems and gaps in legal regulation.

So, cryptocurrency cannot be attributed to any of the existing objects of law, which complicates its use in circulation. Non-acceptance of cryptocurrency as a legal form of payment significantly limits the scope and possibilities of its application.

The main advantages of blockchain technology are protection against unlawful influence by third parties or

network participants; low costs when used as a payment system; reduction in the cost of information storage.

The development of blockchain technology appeared its new generation had changed the existing contract law by introducing a new design into it – a smart contract. The smart contract does not differ in legal content from the usual contract, but its technological features had predetermined of the legal regulation of smart contracts feature. So-called smart contracts give rise to more legal problems than they solve. Their inapplicability to most of the relations of the real sector of the economy casts doubt on the feasibility of further developing this area of using blockchain technology. Unconditional prefer of smart contracts is automatization and optimization of contractual obligations and, as a result, the costs reduction which associated with its costs' execution.

The differences between the blockchain technology and personal data requirements create obstacles to its use in many areas of the economy nowadays. It is needed a correct law about personal data and information for the future develop of blockchain technology.

V. REFERENCES

- [1] Nakamoto, S. (2019). "Bitcoin: a peer-to-peer electronic cash system". Retrieved from: <https://bitcoin.org/bitcoin.pdf>. (last accessed date: 02.01.2020).
- [2] Antonopoulos, A.M. (2015). "Mastering bitcoin". O'Reilly Media, Newton.
- [3] Krajnakova, E., Svazas, M., Valentinas Navickas, V. (2019). "Biomass blockchain as a factor of energetical sustainability development". Entrepreneurship and Sustainability. DOI: 10.9770/jesi.2019.6.3(28).
- [4] Olinder, N.V. (2015). "Forensic characteristics of electronic means of payment and systems". Lex Russica. 10, 128-138.
- [5] Szczepanski, M. (2014). "Bitcoin market, economic and regulation". EPRS Briefing. Retrieved from: [http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2014/140793/LDM_BRI\(2014\)140793_REV1_EN.pdf](http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2014/140793/LDM_BRI(2014)140793_REV1_EN.pdf), (last accessed date: 25.12.2019).
- [6] Saveliev, A.I. (2016). "Contract law 2.0: smart contracts as the beginning of the end of classic contract law". Civil Law Review. 3, 32-60.
- [7] Cellabz, J. (2015). "Blockchain and beyond". Retrieved from: <https://es.scribd.com/document/372163366/Blockchain-Beyond-pdf>, (last accessed date: 12.01.2019)
- [8] Vandina, O., Mkrtychan, Z., Denisov, I., Vechkinzova, Y. (2018). "The tax mechanism of managing the process of formation of information economy in modern Russia". Entrepreneurship and Sustainability. DOI: 10.9770/jesi.2018.6.2(24).
- [9] Internal Revenue Service. (2014). "Virtual currency guidance". Internal Revenue Bulletin. 16
- [10] Faiella R.M. Case 1:14-cr-00243-JSR Document 17. Retrieved from: <https://www.justice.gov/sites/default/files/usao-sdny/legacy/2015/03/25/Faiella%20C%20Robert%20and%20Shrem%20Charle%20Indictment.pdf>. (last accessed date: 23.10.2019).
- [11] Espinosa M.A. IN "The circuit court of the eleventh judicial circuit in and for Miami-Dade county, Florida" Case F14-2923. Retrieved from: https://www.morrisoncohen.com/siteFiles/files/2014_02_06%20-%20Florida%20v_%20Espinosa.pdf. (last accessed date 12.01.2020).
- [12] Houman, B.Sh. (2014). "Regulating bitcoin and blockchain derivatives". Retrieved from: https://cftc.gov/sites/default/files/ido/groups/public/@aboutcftc/documents/file/gmac_100914_bitcoin.pdf (last accessed date: 23.10.2019)
- [13] German Banks Authorized to Store and Sell Cryptocurrency in 2020 <https://news.bitcoin.com/german-banks-authorized-to-store-and-sell-cryptocurrency-in-2020>. (last accessed date: 30.11.2019).
- [14] Lee, J., Long, A., McRae, M., Steiner, J., Handler, S.G. (2015). "Bitcoin Basics: a Primer on Virtual Currencies". Business Law International Vol 16 (1), 21 – 48.
- [15] Skatteverket, D. H. (2014). "Case C-264/14". Retrieved from: <http://curia.europa.eu/juris/document/document.jsf?docid=170305&doclang=EN>, (last accessed date: 02.01.2020)
- [16] Limba, T., Stankevičius, A., Andrulevičius A. (2019). "Cryptocurrency as disruptive technology: theoretical insights". Entrepreneurship and Sustainability. DOI: 10.9770/jesi.2019.6.4(36)
- [17] European Central Bank. (2012). "Virtual Currency Schemes". Retrieved from: <https://www.ecb.europa.eu/pub/pdf/other/virtualcurrencyschemes201210en.pdf>, (last accessed date: 14.10.2019),
- [18] Lunts, L.A. (1992). "Money and monetary obligations in civil law". Statut Press, Moscow.
- [19] On the use of "virtual currencies" in transactions, in particular. Bitcoin. Retrieved from: https://www.cbr.ru/press/pr/?file=04092017_183512if2017-09-04T18_31_05.htm, (last accessed date: 25.12.2019)
- [20] Krylov, O.M. (2011). "To the question of the legal category "money substitute"". Administrativnoe i municipal'noe pravo. 8, 56-61.
- [21] Mutter, G. (2016). "Legal uncertainty of cryptocurrency". Yurist. 16, 2.
- [22] Federal Law dated 10.12.2003 No. 173-Ф3 "On Currency Regulation and Currency Control". (2003). Collection of legislation of the Russian Federation. 50.
- [23] Sklovsky, K.I., Kostko, V.S. (2018). "About the concept of a thing. Money. The property". Vestnik ekonomicheskogo pravosudiya Rossijskoj Federacii. 7, 115-143.
- [24] Saveliev, A.I. (2017). "Cryptocurrencies in the system of civil rights". Zakon. 8, 136-153.
- [25] BBVA research. (2015). Smart contracts: the ultimate automation of trust? Digital Economy Outlook. Retrieved from: https://www.bbva.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/10/Digital_Economy_Outlook_Oct15_Cap1.pdf, (last accessed date: 12.01.2020)
- [26] Volos, A.A. (2018). "Smart contracts and civil law principles". Russian Justitia. 12, 5-7.
- [27] Lessig, L. (2006). Code: and other laws of cyberspace, version 2.0. Basic Books Press, New York.
- [28] Hobbes, T. (1991). "Leviathan or the matter, form and power of a common wealth ecclesiast call and civil". Mysl' Press, Moscow.
- [29] Marx, K., Engels, F. (1959). "A contribution to the critique of political economy". Politizdat Press, Moscow.
- [30] Werbach, K., Cornell, N. (2017). "Contracts ex machine". Duke Law Journal. 67, 313-382.
- [31] Szabo, N. (1997). "Formalizing and securing relationships on public networks". First Monday. 2 (9). DOI: 10.5210/fm.v2i9.548.
- [32] Guerlin, G. (2017). Sur les smart contracts. Droit de la intellectuelle et du. 10, 512-515.
- [33] Federal Law dated March 18, 2019 No. 34-Ф3 "On Amendments to Parts One, Two and Article 1124 of Part Three of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation". 2019. Collection of legislation of the Russian Federation. 2019. 12.
- [34] Federal Law dated 06.04.2011 N 63-Ф3 "On electronic signature". 2011. Collection of legislation of the Russian Federation. 15.

- [35] Kamalyan, V.M. (2019). "Concept and legal features of smart contracts". *Yurist*. 4, 20-27.
- [36] Bogdanova, E.E. (2019). "Problems of smart contracts application in transactions in virtual property". *Lex Russica*. 7, 108-118. DOI: 10.17803/1729-5920.2019.152.7.
- [37] Gromova, E.A. (2018). "Smart contracts in Russia: an attempt to determine the legal nature". *Law and Digital Economy*. 2, 34-37.
- [38] Raskin, M. (2017). "The law and legality of smart contracts". *Georgetown Law Technology Review*. 1, 304 -341.
- [39] Saveliev, A.I. (2017). "Some legal aspects of the use of smart contracts and blockchain technologies in accordance with the Russian Law". *Zakon*. 5, 94-117.
- [40] Joshua, A.T. (2014). "Fairfield. Smart contracts, Bitcoin bots, and consumer protection". *Washington and Lee Law Review Online*. 71 (2), 35-50.
- [41] Cieplak, J., Leefatt, S. (2017). "Smart contracts: a smart way to automate performance". *Georgetown Law Technology Review*. 1 (2), 417-427.
- [42] Belov, V. A. (2015). "On the consensus and reality of a lease". *Pravo i Ekonomika*. 3, 54-56.
- [43] Scholz, H.L. (2017). "Algorithmic contracts". *Stanford Technology Law Review*. 20 (2), 128-169.
- [44] Zittrain, J.L. (2008). "The future of the Internet and how to stop it". Yale University Press & Penguin UK, London.
- [45] Kuznetsov, E.N. (2017). "Self-protection of the right to voluntary execution of obligations". *Russian Juridical Journal*. 5, 152-156.
- [46] Malko, A.V., Subochev, V.V., Sheriev, A.M. (2010). "Rights, freedoms and legitimate interests: problems of legal support". *Infra-M Press, Moscow*.
- [47] Kurdanov, V.O. (2017). "Self-defense as an independent type of mechanism for protecting the rights and freedoms of man and citizen". *Gosudarstvennaya vlast' i mestnoe samoupravlenie*. 4, 10-14.
- [48] Sklaroff, J. (2017). "Smart contracts and the cost of inflexibility". *University of Pennsylvania Law Review*. 166, 263-303.
- [49] Yermack, D. (2017). "Corporate governance and blockchains". *Review of Finance*. 21, 7-31.
- [50] Sannikova, L.V. (2019). "Blockchain in corporate governance: problems and prospects". *Pravo i ekonomika*. 4, 27-36.
- [51] Federal Law of December 26, 1995 N 208-FZ (as amended on July 3, 2016) "On Joint-Stock Companies". 1996. *Collected Legislation of the Russian Federation*. 1.
- [52] Churilov, A.Yu. (2019). "Principles of the European Union General Regulation on the protection of personal data (GDPR): problems and prospects of implementation". *Vestnik of the Omsk Law Academy*. 1, 29-35.
- [53] Article 4 of EU GDPR. Retrieved from: <https://www.privacy-regulation.eu/en/article-4-definitions-GDPR.htm> (last accessed date: 02.01.2020)
- [54] Art. 3 of the Personal Data Act. Retrieved from: https://legalacts.ru/doc/152_FZ-o-personalnyh-dannyh/glava-1/statja-3/, (last accessed date: 25.12.2019).
- [55] *Scarlet Extended SA v. SABAM*, ECJ, Case C 70/10. 24 November 2011. Retrieved from: <http://curia.europa.eu/juris/liste.jsf?language=en&num=C-70/10>, (last accessed date: 23.10.2019)
- [56] *Patrick Breyer v. Bundesrepublik Deutschland*, ECJ, Case C-582/14. 19 October 2016. Retrieved from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A62014CJ0582>, (last accessed date: 14.10.2019)
- [57] Mirchandani, A. (2019). "The GDPR-blockchain paradox: exempting permissioned blockchains from the GDPR". *Media & Entertainment. Law Journal*. 4, 1201-1241.